

EIT Detection of Juvenile and Knot Wood in Southern Pine Logs

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ABSTRACT

The juvenile wood type is produced by southern pine trees during their first 10 years of growth producing a significant volume of wood at tree center having inferior properties that decrease lumber value. Increased volumes of lumber are influenced by juvenile wood as intensive plantation silviculture increases early tree growth. Research has shown that knowledge of knot location in logs prior to sawing has the potential to significantly increase lumber value yield. Detection of juvenile and knot wood prior to sawing logs will allow application of sawing patterns that place these wood types into locations or products that have reduced influence on the final lumber value. This study tested an electrical impedance tomography (EIT) scanner for detection of juvenile and knot wood in southern pine. EIT and CT images were compared to determine the accuracy of juvenile and knot wood detection by EIT technology.

Keywords Electrical impedance tomography, juvenile wood, knot wood, southern pine

1 INTRODUCTION

During the early growth of many tree species, a wood type known as *juvenile wood* is formed in the early years of growth. Tasissa and Burkhart (1998) determined that 10 years was the most precise average age defining the period of juvenile wood growth for the loblolly pine species. In pine plantations fast-growing, genetically improved seedlings are initially planted at wide spacings, meaning that juvenile wood may comprise between 60 to 80 percent of total stem volume of the wood harvested in early thinnings (Bendtsen, 1978). Juvenile wood gradually transitions to mature wood over one or more years after the initial 10-year period of growth. The wood type developed during this intermediate stage between juvenile and mature wood is termed *transition wood* (Zobel and Sprague, 1998). The properties of transition wood combine those of juvenile and mature wood with the gradation of properties in proportion to the degree of transition to mature wood.

Juvenile wood has several negative properties that influence its utilization. Chemically, juvenile wood has lower cellulose content, higher hemi-cellulose content, higher pentosan content, lower polysaccharide content, higher alcohol-benzene content and higher lignin content (Zobel and Sprague, 1998). Juvenile wood characteristics also include, thinner cell walls, larger lumen diameters, higher S₂ layer fibril angle, shorter fiber length, lower specific gravity, lower transverse shrinkage, higher longitudinal shrinkage, higher moisture content, a lower percentage of latewood, lower stiffness and lower strength (Bowyer et al. 2003). Juvenile wood shrinks up to 10 times more in the longitudinal direction as compared to mature wood (Lamb and Wengert, 1987). The high amounts of shrinkage results in a high degree of warp and value loss in lumber containing it.

Knots comprise, by far, the majority of defects that influence lumber value in both hardwood and softwood species. The prevalence of knots in logs is explained by the fact that the structures are tree limbs that growth at tree pith during the first year of tree life. The limbs, and resultant knots, continue to grow outward from tree pith, increasing in diameter with tree age. When limbs die and shed from the tree the knots are overgrown by clear wood but the influence of knot presence is indicated in this overgrown clear wood for many years. As will be indicated in the results below, the presence of grain distortion within the clear wood laid down over knots may pose a problem in the detection of knot presence by means of the electrical fields produced by the EIT technique.

Several researchers have investigated the benefit of scanning hardwood species logs for defects prior to sawing followed by computer analysis to position defects in lumber to optimize lumber value (Tsolakides, 1969; Richards et al. 1980; Peter, 1967; Steele et al. 1994). Their estimates of potential lumber value improvement ranged from 9 to 21 percent. Wagner and Taylor (1975) estimated a value

yield increase of 43 percent from simulated scanning followed by computer-optimized sawing of southern yellow pine sawlogs.

Researchers have tested the available technologies for internal scanning of sawlogs. Among the known potential methods of log scanning for internal defects, CT imaging is the most frequently investigated solution for obtaining images (Araman and Schmoldt, 1995; Funt and Bryant, 1987; Holoyen and Birkeland, 1999; Schmoldt et al. 1993; Zhu and Beex, 1994). NMR scanners have also been tested for this purpose and acceptable images were produced (Chang et al. 1989). However, both technologies remain too slow to be applied for industrial log scanning and both are relatively expensive technologies. Schafer (1999) disclosed an apparatus based on the application of ultrasound to detect localized anomalies such as knots and voids. Square cants have been scanned successfully in a sawmill by this ultrasound technology. However, technical problems with maintaining transducer contact with log surfaces has limited commercial application for its use for log scanning. Kaestner (1999) described a microwave device that successfully produced knot images from log scans. While results were promising, some technical problems remained to be resolved and no commercial device is available. White (1996) tested an Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) device for detecting internal rot in wooden poles but no attempt to detect knots with the large capacitor electrodes that were employed was attempted. Salvolainen et al. (1996) successfully developed an EIT system capable of imaging internal log images showing knots. However, the sensors employed metallic screws which render their method impossible to utilize for the scanning of moving logs.

Steele and Cooper (2004) have been granted U. S. Patent No. 6,784,672 for the Through-Log Density Detector (TLDD). This is an EIT device for detecting differential densities in logs such as for wood types (juvenile and compression) and knot or rot presence. Electrodes are non-penetrating and one embodiment of electrode configuration allows the movement of sawlogs past electrodes.

2 OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study was to determine juvenile wood and knot wood detection capabilities of the TLDD, in static mode, by comparison of cross-sectional TLDD with CT images.

2.1 Experimental procedures

One southern pine tree of approximately 30.48 cm (12-in.) diameter at breast height was selected and felled at a 30.48-cm (12-in.) stump. A 3.66 m (12-foot) log was cut from the felled tree and 3 log cross sections of approximately 121.92 cm (48-in.) in length were subsequently cut from the full-length log. Sections 121.92 cm (48-in.) long were selected to provide log sections containing a minimum of one knot whorl per log section while minimizing the weight of specimens during manipulation for transport and scanning. Following initial harvesting, the log sections were stored in cold storage at 34°C until 24 hours prior to scanning and at this time were allowed to warm to ambient temperature. Log sections were debarked to allow full electrode contact with debarked surface and scanned along the log section length at 5-mm intervals with a GE Lightspeed CT scanner. Images of log cross sections were created from CT imaging software.

Following CT scanning, TLDD scanning was performed utilizing eight 25.4 mm (1.0-in.) metallic equidistant electrodes attached to an elastic band. Elastic band diameter was selected so as to maintain approximately $0.70 \text{ lb}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ ($10 \text{ lb}\cdot\text{in}^{-2}$) pressure on log surface.

Figure 1 provides a block diagram of the scanning TLDD setup employed in the study. A radio frequency signal was generated and coupled to a current source. By the TLDD method, current was applied between one adjacent electrode pair with the resultant voltage sensed at the remaining 7 adjacent electrode pairs. This process was performed for each of the 7 remaining adjacent electrode pairs resulting in 64 observations per cross sectional log scan. Log sections were scanned at 25.4 mm (1-in.) intervals over the span of the log section length, beginning and ending approximately 10.16 cm (4 in.) from log section ends to reduce the end-effect influence. Digital EIT images of the log cross sections were created from TLDD log scan data with EIDORS imaging software (Vauhkonen et al. 2000).

False colors in TLDD images were replaced with color values from a colorbar legend in Matlab® computer software. TLDD image colors ranging from dark blue to dark red were replaced with color

values ranging from 2 to 23, with the color value 2 representing dark blue; 4 representing blue; 9 representing light blue; 14 representing yellow; 18 representing orange; 19 representing light red; 20 representing red and 23 representing dark red as shown in Figure 2.

TLDD cross-sectional images were compared to CT images, at the same location along log length, to determine accuracy of TLDD juvenile wood and knot size and location estimation. For this purpose, the juvenile wood area was manually outlined in the TLDD and CT images as shown in Figure 2. The software Microsoft[®] Paint traced juvenile wood and knot wood peripheries based on specified definitions of these wood types. For purposes of this delineation, juvenile wood was defined in the TLDD images as the circular area near log cross section center with color indicator values ranging from 18 to 23. A color indicator value of 23 in the TLDD images indicated a stronger influence on the EIT electrical field due to the higher moisture content of juvenile wood. The color value of 23 was closest to the center of the log, indicating the higher moisture of the juvenile wood developed earliest in tree growth. As the juvenile wood transitioned toward a lower mature wood moisture content, the influence on EIT electrical field lessened and the color indicator value of 23 decreased to approximately 18 and finally, to 14. The area having a color indicator value of 18 was included in the area of TLDD image defined as juvenile wood, but the area having a color indicator value of 14 was excluded.

Researchers felt that determining the difference in juvenile wood size between TLDD and CT images was an adequate measure of the accuracy of TLDD imaging. This was true because juvenile wood was always positioned correctly in the TLDD images at log center. Difference in juvenile area definition between TLDD and CT images occurred only at the periphery of the juvenile wood core allowing area to be a proxy for positional error computation.

In the CT images, juvenile wood was defined manually as the area of wood contained within the first 10 growth rings. Following delineation of juvenile wood in both TLDD and CT images, Matlab[®] software, developed for this purpose, computed the difference in area defined in each.

Knots in the TLDD images differed from juvenile wood in that they varied in color indicator value depending on knot numbers and locations at their cross-sectional positions. Their color indicator values varied from 14 to 18 through 23 depending on their size and location within the cross section. A few larger knots, and those nearer to log surface, had a stronger influence on the EIT electrical field. As was the case for juvenile wood, this stronger influence resulted in color indicator values from 18 to 23 for knots. Most of the knots had less influence on the field and had a color indicator value of 14.

The knots indicated by color values from 14 to 23 in the TLDD images were visually identified and outlined with Microsoft[®] Paint software in the same manner described above for the juvenile wood areas. Figure 3 shows a CT image with a single knot outlined by this procedure. Knot location and area in the TLDD images were compared to knot location and area in the CT images. Areas of all TLDD knots were larger than those in the CT knot images. Therefore, CT knot area was subtracted from the TLDD knot area to obtain a positive measure of TLDD knot size error, measured in square inches, by which TLDD knot images exceeded CT knot images.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the TLDD scanning system

Knot depth from the log surface in CT and TLDD images was measured along a radial line from log center passing through knot center to the log surface as shown in Figure 4. TLDD knot depths were always less than those in the CT images. Therefore, the lower TLDD knot depth from the log surface

was subtracted from the CT depth to obtain a positive measure of TLDD knot position error. Figure 5 illustrates the definition of the knot position and error variables.

Figure 2: Cross-sectional CT (a) and TLDD (b) images showing the method for outlining juvenile wood

Figure 3: Cross-sectional CT (a) and TLDD (b) images showing the method for outlining knot wood

Figure 4: Cross-sectional CT (a) and TLDD (b) images showing the method for determining knot distance from the log surface along a radial line from log center to log surface

Figure 5: Image illustrating the definition of the knot position and TLDD knot position error

3 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

A completely randomized experimental design was employed to compare CT and TLDD log scanning methods. The CT and TLDD scanning methods were entered as independent treatment variables while juvenile wood area was the dependent variable in analysis-of-variance (ANOVA) (equation 1). All comparison-of-means tests were performed at the 0.05 level of significance.

$$\text{Juvenile Wood Area} = \mu + \text{METHOD} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where: μ = overall mean juvenile wood area (cm^2)
 METHOD = CT or TLDD log scanning method
 ε = error term

4 RESULTS

In equation 1, the METHOD treatment variable was found to be significant, with a p-value of less than 0.0001, satisfying Fisher's Protected LSD Procedure at the 0.05 level allowing comparison-of-means tests to be performed. Figure 6 shows the comparison-of-means test results for determining mean juvenile wood area by the log scanning methods. The TLDD log scanning system yielded a mean juvenile wood area response that was a significant 29.4 cm^2 (20-percent) larger than that yielded from the CT images. This result indicates a consistent overestimation of TLDD juvenile wood area caused by the definition that we adopted for the TLDD juvenile wood core area. Redefinition of the value code defining the outer limit of juvenile wood areas would be a simple means to correct this overestimation error.

Juvenile wood location error was back calculated based on the difference in mean radii of the CT and TLDD images. Mean radius of the CT image was 6.89 cm (2.70 in.) and for the TLDD was 7.49 cm (2.95 in.). Therefore, mean juvenile wood position error was 0.6 cm (0.25 in.), or about 9 percent.

Figure 6: Juvenile wood area versus scanning method

Figure 7a shows TLDD knot position error as a function of knot depth. A strong relationship, $R^2 = 0.99$, between the error in TLDD knot position and CT knot distance from log surface was observed. TLDD knot position error increased as the CT knot distance from the surface increased at a rate of $1.77 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$. The fact that there exists a positive relationship between TLDD knot position estimation and depth of knot from log surface in the CT image is not surprising. TLDD knots are nearly always imaged

at a position at, or near, the log surface. The constant position of the TLDD knots causes knot position error to increase directly with CT knot distance from log surface.

Figure 7b shows TLDD knot size error as a function of knot depth. The error in knot size estimation also increases directly with distance from log surface for a similar reason. The knot areas, always near log surface, in the TLDD images are of nearly uniform size regardless of CT knot size and distance from log center. As previously discussed, knots originate in the central tree pith and grow in size with the tree growth. Therefore, knots near tree center will be the smaller knots of initial size and knot size will tend to grow larger with distance from tree center until the limb dies. Subtraction of the CT imaged, smaller knot areas at tree center from a nearly uniform knot area in TLDD images will inherently result in a decreasing error in knot size estimation as CT knot distance from log surface decreases. The R^2 value for the relationship is 0.29.

Figure 7: TLDD position error (a) and TLDD knot size error (b) correlated to distance from log surface

The reason for the TLDD knot area and position errors stem, at least in part, from the previously discussed fact that knot influence in clear wood extends well beyond knot location. The single knot in figure 3 is a relatively small 25.4 mm diameter knot but can easily be seen that the growth rings are distorted from terminating knot periphery to the log surface. Often the distorted wood influenced by knot presence is composed of compression wood. Compression wood is denser and has lower moisture content than mature wood. The higher density of this wood type appeared to increase the EIT response in clear wood from termination of knot area to the log surface. This response increase was nearly as strong as that produced by juvenile wood causing a false positive knot image near the log surface in TLDD images.

It is clear from the TLDD knot position and size results, that more accurate imaging of TLDD knot position and size are needed to refine this technology. Such accuracy may be added by increasing electrode numbers from 8 to 16, by adjustments in the EIDORS software, or other modifications to the system. Extreme accuracy for the purpose of identifying knot locations for sawing optimization is not required. However, considerable increase in the current accuracy of TLDD knot imaging will be needed prior to commercialization of the technology.

5 SUMMARY

Images produced by CT and TLDD technologies were produced by cross-sectional scanning of a loblolly pine sawlog at 25.4 mm (1-in.) intervals along log length. The TLDD employed EIT methodology with an 8-electrode elastic band. TLDD estimate of juvenile wood area was relatively accurate with 20 percent larger area and 9 percent position error compared with images from CT tomograms. Relatively simple modification of the color value indicating juvenile wood margin was judged by researchers as a feasible means to correct the consistent TLDD overestimation of juvenile wood size. However, for the detection of knots in TLDD images, there were large area and positional errors that were highly correlated with increasing knot depth from the log surface. These errors were partially attributed to the influence of knots on adjacent clear wood in producing the dense compression wood type that increased EIT response. Increased electrode numbers and further research to evaluate the compression wood interference in accurate knot imaging will potentially allow the TLDD technology to be utilized to scan sawlogs. These scans can be used for the application of optimum sawing patterns to increase lumber value during sawing.

6 REFERENCES

- ARAMAN P A and SCHMOLDT D L, (1995), Scanning system, technology worth a look, *Wood and Wood Products*, 100 5, 138-142.
- BENDTSEN B A, (1978), Properties of wood from improved and intensively managed trees, *Forest Prod. J.*, 28 10, 61-72.
- BOWYER J L, SHMULSKY R and HAYGREEN J G, (2003), *Forest Products and Wood Science, an Introduction*, 4th ed. ISU Press, A Blackwell Company.
- CHANG S J, OLSON J R and WANG P C, (1989), NMR imaging of internal features in wood, *Forest Prod. J.*, 39 6, 43-49.
- FUNT B V and BRYANT E. C, (1987), Detection of internal log defects by automatic interpretation of computer tomography images, *Forest Prod. J.*, 37 1, 56-62.
- HOLOYEN S and BIRKELAND R, (1999), Industrial methods for internal scanning of log defects, A progress report on an ongoing project in Norway, Scanning Technology and Process Optimization, *Miller publications*, 61-73.
- KAESTNER A, (1999), Polarimetry based wood scanning: theory and experiments, *Licen. Eng. Thesis*, Dept. of Signals and Systems, Chalmers University of Technology, 69 p.
- LAMB F M and WENGERT E M, (1987), The drying properties of lumber containing juvenile wood, *Forest Product Research Society Annual Meeting*, June 21- 24. Louisville, Kentucky.
- PETER R K, (1967), Lumber grade yield from yellow-poplar, *Forest Prod. J.*, 17 11, 19-24
- RICHARDS D B, ADKINS W K, HALLOCK H and BULGRIN E H, (1980), Lumber Values from computerized simulation of hardwood log sawing, *Res. Pap. FPL-356, USDA Forest Serv., Forest Prod. Lab*, 28 p.
- SAVOLAINEN J P, KARJALAINEN P A and VAUHKONEN M, (1996), An electrical impedance tomography measurement system for experimental use, *Review of Scientific Instrumentation*, 67 10, 3605-3609, American Institute of Physics.
- SCHAFFER M E, (1999), Ultrasonic apparatus for characterizing wooden members using a measurement of wave distortion, *International publication Number: WO 99/44049*.
- SCHMOLDT D L, ZHU D and CONNERS R W, (1993), Nondestructive evaluation of hardwood logs using automated interpretation of CT images, *In Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, ed. By Thompson, D.O. and Chimenti, D.E. Vol. 12, Plenum Press, New York, 2257-2264.
- STEELE P H and COOPER J E, (2004), Through-Log Density Detector, U.S. Patent 6,784,672.
- STEELE P H, HARLESS T E G, WAGNER F G, KUMAR L, and TAYLOR F W, (1994), Increased lumber value from optimum orientation of internal defects with respect to sawing patterns in hardwood sawlogs, *Forest Prod. J.*, 44 3, 69-72.
- TASSISSA G and BURKHART H E, (1998), Juvenile-mature wood demarcation in loblolly pine trees, *Wood and Fiber Science*, 30 2, 119-127.
- TSOLAKIDES J A, (1969), Simulation model for log yield study, *Forest Prod. J.*, 19 7, 21-26
- VAUHKONEN M, LIONHEART W R B, HEIKKINEN L M, VAUHKONEN P J and KAIPIO J P, (2000), A Matlab package for the EIDORS project to reconstruct two-dimensional EIT images, *Department of Applied Physics Report Series ISSN 0788-4672*, Department of Applied Physics, University of Kuopio, Kuopio, Finland.

WAGNER F G and TAYLOR F W, (1975), Simulated sawing with a chipping headrig, *Forest Prod. J.*, 25 10, 24-28.

WHITE N B, (1996), Development of phase-sensitive electrical impedance tomography for detection of decay in wood. *Ph. D. Thesis*, Institute of Science and Technology, University of Manchester, 195 p.

ZHU D and BEECH A, (1994), Robust spatial auto-regressive modeling for hardwood log inspection, *J. of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, 5 1, 41-51.

ZOBEL B J and SPRAGUE J R, (1998), *Juvenile Wood in Forest Trees*, Springer-Verlag, New York, New York, 300 p.